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Orientalism, Desire and the Politics of Looking in Oscar Wilde's *Salomé*

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Abstract:

This paper examines Oscar Wilde's *Salomé* as a site for the construction of the 'Oriental woman' through the intersecting frameworks of Orientalism, gender, and the male gaze, examining how Wilde's titular Salomé becomes the site upon which Western fantasies of eroticism, conquest, and violence are projected. By analysing Wilde's representation of Salomé within the broader context of 19th-century Orientalist discourse, this paper argues that her characterisation perpetuates a deeply gendered and racialised fantasy that positions the 'Oriental woman' as both a seductive threat and a necessary victim. The play situates Salomé as a visual and symbolic spectacle: a woman simultaneously virginal and hypersexual, sacred and profane, with Salomé emerging as the ultimate fetishised figure of the colonial imagination and whose body becomes a space for the fulfilment of repressed Western desires. Salomé, in the end, is not merely a literary figure, but a projection of Western anxieties about race, sexuality, and empire.

Keywords: Orientalism, gender, sexuality, the male gaze.

Introduction: The Construction of the 'Oriental Woman'

For the men of the Enlightenment, the continents of Asia and Africa served as symbolic opposites of Europe, providing reference points against which the West could assert its progress in reason, aesthetics, economy, and governance. This binary logic, which was central to Enlightenment epistemology, positioned non-Western cultures as deviations from a presumed universal standard rooted in European values. Consequently, Asia and Africa were portrayed as not only different but also as deficient and lacking in the rationality, civility, and progress that Enlightenment discourse attributed to Europe.

The reductive treatment of the 'Orient' became a well-established trope within travel literature, ethnographic accounts, and early anthropological writings by the mid-nineteenth century. These texts propagated ideas and projected fantasies, anxieties and desires onto the East, thereby transforming it into a symbolic site upon which the Western imagination could project its unconscious impulses. This symbolic and representative treatment constituted the latent structure of Orientalism, which, as a cultural and ideological framework, sustained and normalised asymmetrical power relations between the West and the non-West. In this context, the Orient functioned less as a geographical or cultural entity and more as a constructed 'other' that served the ideological and political interests of imperial Europe.

The term 'oriental', which described artistic, literary, and scholarly depictions of the East and 'Eastern' subjects during the nineteenth century, gained a critical redefinition after the publication of Edward Said's *Orientalism* in 1978. Said argued that the Orient was not a creation stemming from divisive geographical lines but was a constructed imaginary which posited the Oriental as the polar opposite of the Occidental, characterising the Orient as "irrational, exotic, erotic, despotic and heathen, and thereby securing the West in contrast as rational, familiar, moral,

just and Christian” (Lewis 16). Said further elaborates that Orientalism operates as a gendered and sexualised mode of representation, shaped profoundly by patriarchal and colonial fantasies. For Said, Orientalism takes a perverse shape as a male “power fantasy” that sexualises a feminised Orient for Western power and possession. He writes: “(Orientalism) viewed itself and its subject matter with sexist blinders. This is especially evident in the writing of travellers and novelists: women are usually the creatures of a male power-fantasy. They express unlimited sensuality, they are more or less stupid, and above all they are willing” (Said 207). This fantasy, along with the perceived inferiority of the Orient, allowed for the white male gaze to paint the ‘Oriental woman’ with imagined availability that allows the Western male gaze to articulate desires that would be socially and morally unacceptable if directed at white women. This gaze thus relegated her to the margins of both gendered and racialised subjecthood. The ‘Oriental woman’, therefore, becomes a fetishised figure that is constructed to satisfy desires that could not be legitimately acted upon within Western moral and social codes.

This process of eroticisation and othering is illustrated by Anne McClintock in *Imperial Leather*. In the book, she highlights how such fantasies were spatialised in colonial imaginaries by providing the example of Henry Rider Haggard’s *King Solomon’s Mines* (1885). In the novel, a map drawn by a Portuguese explorer allegedly depicts the path to the diamond mines of Kukuanialand in Southern Africa (Haggard 30).

Fig: Map of Kukuanaland

McClintock notes that when the map is inverted, it reveals the outline of a spread-eagled female body, with clearly marked sexual organs: a vaginal opening leading to a cave, and behind it the pit called “Idol’s Pit”, from which male explorers emerge, triumphant with diamonds (McClintock 2-3, Haggard 30). On the map, the three mountains that resemble female genitalia are called the “Three Witches” (Haggard 121), a name befitting the women that occidental discourse had decreed existed in such places. The naming reinforces the gendered and racialised coding of the land as simultaneously seductive, dangerous, and in need of subjugation. The terrain, which is feminised and explicitly sexualised, becomes a metaphor for colonial conquest, and the map becomes a cartographic fantasy that literalises the conflation of land and the female body.

This representational strategy reflects a broader ideological pattern in which colonised women are doubly objectified as racialised others and as hypersexualised bodies. The ‘Oriental woman’, in particular, emerges as a fetishised figure whose imagined exoticism functions to rationalise the acts of sexual objectification and domination that often accompany imperial enterprise. The commodification of her sexuality renders her both dangerous and desirable, a

paradox that sustains her appeal while legitimising her subjugation. ‘Oriental women’ were fetishised and their sexuality was commoditised as exotic, promiscuous and mysterious.

The trope of the hypersexualised, submissive, and mysterious ‘Oriental woman’ served not only as a mechanism for erotic fantasy but also as a justification for the objectification and often violent subjugation of colonised female bodies. This trope is dramatised in David Henry Hwang’s *M. Butterfly*, where the character Song Liling articulates the West’s eroticised assumptions about the East: “Her mouth says no, but her eyes say yes. The West believes the East, deep down, wants to be dominated ... You expect Oriental countries to submit to your guns, and you expect Oriental women to be submissive to your men” (Hwang 83). In this dialogue, Hwang exposes the persistent entanglement of sexual politics with imperial ideology. The ‘Oriental woman’ is imagined as complicit in her own domination, and her body and will are presumed to be aligned with the desires of the coloniser. Taken together, these cultural texts and critical insights demonstrate how Orientalism functions as a deeply gendered apparatus, as the commodification of the woman’s sexuality, which is represented as both dangerous and desirable, renders her an object of voyeuristic pleasure and imperial control.

This dynamic is vividly illustrated in Oscar Wilde’s *Salomé*, where the titular character’s body becomes the locus of a layered gaze. Wilde’s play, though situated within a biblical framework, reproduces orientalist conventions by rendering Salomé as both an erotic spectacle and a symbol of Eastern otherness. Her body becomes a site of visual consumption for both characters within the text and the Western audience outside of it. In this way, *Salomé* exemplifies how Western literature participates in and perpetuates the visual economy of Orientalism that facilitates a voyeuristic mode of engagement rooted in colonial desire and domination. Salomé’s

representation not only reiterates stereotypes of exotic sensuality but also exposes the mechanisms by which literature constructs and sustains imperial ideologies through aesthetics.

Salomé and the Spectacle of Oriental Femininity

“A woman in the culture of privileged Europeans is first and foremost a sight to be looked at” (Berger 3:15-21). Berger’s observation captures the visual politics that structure Western aesthetic traditions and colonial and patriarchal fantasies. It is through this lens that Oscar Wilde’s *Salomé* must be understood, as the play positions its titular character as an object of visual voyeurism and consumption. *Salomé* had long circulated within Western literary and artistic traditions as a symbol of deviant female sexuality. By the late nineteenth century, *Salomé* became a popular figure in literature and art and was a muse to Flaubert, Mallarmé, Huysmans, and Maeterlinck. Shaped by racialised and gendered fantasies, she gradually evolved from the dancing girl in the Bible to the archetypal ‘Oriental woman’. This construction aligns *Salomé* with a broader legacy of representations of the ‘Oriental woman’ in nineteenth-century Western art and literature, where she is repeatedly rendered as erotic and exotic.

Thus, decades of French literature had evoked the image of the Orient as a “powerfully consuming unknown, a forbidden erotic figure, a grotesquely uncivilised world of violence...” (Lowe 214). There was thus a thriving market for oriental fantasies, where the exotic and erotic came together for the European gaze, and it was within this cultural and artistic milieu in Paris that Wilde envisioned his play, *Salomé*. Wilde originally wrote the play in French and wanted the French stage actress Sara Bernhardt, who had previously portrayed another iconic figure of feminised Orientalism, Cleopatra in Sardou and Moreau’s *Cléopâtre* (1890), to be his *Salomé*. Wilde explicitly conceived of *Salomé* as a visual and aesthetic spectacle, and Bernhardt planned to have her hair powdered blue and adapt her Cleopatra costume to the requisites of *Salomé*

(Marland 351-353). Bernhardt's costume decision underscores the performative continuity between these two archetypes of exotic femininity. Salomé, like Cleopatra, emerges as a tool for symbolic utility: she is not a person but a projection of Orientalist, patriarchal and colonial fantasies.

Throughout the play, Salomé is looked at. She is the object of unrelenting male attention, reinforcing the gendered logic of the gaze. Her step-father Herod's voyeuristic fixation is both explicit and unsettling, and Herodotus, Salomé's mother, asks her husband, "Why are you always gazing at her?" (Wilde 31). Salomé is acutely aware that she is being watched and observes, "Why does the Tetrarch look at me all the while with his mole's eyes under his shaking eyelids? It is strange that the husband of my mother looks at me like that. I know not what it means. In truth, yes, I know it" (9). Salomé's recognition of the male gaze reveals her simultaneous vulnerability and agency within this regime of visual power. She is constructed as naive and virginal, yet she is not unaware of the symbolic currency of her own body. As the 'Oriental woman', she maintains the façade of innocence required by her role, preserving the distinction between sexual inexperience and sensual potency, confessing to the former, but possessing the ability to use the gaze to her advantage.

This complex duality is made explicit in her symbolic connection with the moon, which is anthropomorphised in explicitly gendered terms. Early in the play, Salomé gazes at the moon and says, "The moon is cold and chaste. I am sure she is a virgin, she has a virgin's beauty. Yes, she is a virgin. She has never defiled herself. She has never abandoned herself to men, like the other goddesses" (Wilde 11). Here, the moon serves as a mirror for Salomé's own constructed identity. She is an emblem of purity, aloofness, and unattainability. Later, when she lays her eyes on Jokanaan for the first time, she makes a similar comparison, observing, "He is like an image of

silver. I am sure he is chaste as the moon is" (19). This transference of chaste symbolism onto Jokanaan underscores Salomé's inversion of the typical gender dynamic. She becomes the desiring subject rather than the passive object. However, her desire is coded as dangerous, transgressive, and ultimately destructive. Salomé develops an uncontrollable desire for Jokanaan and wishes to possess him despite his protestations. His repeated rejections fuel her obsession and transform her desire into a violent will to possession to the point where she will have him against his will, dead or alive. This desire culminates in her demand for his head, a literalisation of the domination she is denied when he was alive.

From the outset of the play, Wilde undermines the illusion of Salomé's innocence by foregrounding the dangerous power of her visual presence. In one of the earliest lines, the Page of Herodias observes that the moon is "like a woman rising from a tomb. She is like a dead woman. You would fancy she was looking for dead things" (Wilde 1). When he notices the Young Syrian's stirring desire for the princess, he warns, "Why do you look at her? You must not look at her ... Something terrible may happen" (2). This admonition immediately establishes the gaze as a site of peril and foreshadows the catastrophic consequences of desire. The act of looking is imbued with risk, casting Salomé not as a mere object of beauty but as a figure whose visibility exerts a fatal influence.

Towards the end of the play, the moon that Salomé once identified with chastity and restraint undergoes a radical transformation. Herod observes the moon and remarks:

She is like a mad woman, a mad woman who is seeking everywhere for lovers. She is naked too. She is quite naked. The clouds are seeking to clothe her nakedness, but she will not let them. She shows herself naked in the sky. She reels through the clouds like a drunken

woman ... I am sure she is looking for lovers. Does she not reel like a drunken woman? She is like a mad woman, is she not?" (Wilde 27)

The transformed moon becomes a projection of the Occident's eroticised fear and revulsion to Salomé's metamorphosis from the virginal object of desire to a vengeful and sexualised agent whose assertion of desire transgresses patriarchal and moral boundaries.

Through the mutable symbolism of the moon, Wilde projects the volatile oscillation between purity and eroticism, seen in the juxtaposed representation of an ideal of untouched femininity through the virgin Salomé, who is the object of Herod's escalating desire and Salomé's transformation into a lustful, vengeful temptress. The juxtaposition of virginity and eroticism, of purity and temptation, encapsulates the Orientalist fantasy that constructs the Eastern woman as both sacred and profane, which is an alluring contradiction that invites both possession and punishment. Salomé is a vision of this kind of male gaze that has created this paradox, reflecting the enduring fantasy of the 'Oriental woman' who is alluring precisely because she is at once pure and corrupt, submissive and dangerous. In Salomé, this fantasy becomes both spectacle and cautionary tale, illustrating how the figure of the 'Oriental woman' is constructed not as a subject with agency, but as a site of projected anxieties, eroticism, and desire.

Salomé as Subject: Female Agency and Inverting the Gaze

In the play, gazing functions as both a narrative and ideological device that governs gendered and racialised power relations. The male-female relationships in *Salomé* unfold as a visual economy of looking and being looked at, where desire is both incited and punished through acts of voyeurism and spectatorship. Her request to the Young Syrian to uncover the cistern where Jokanaan is imprisoned is transactional: she offers her gaze as a reward. "I will look at you through the muslin veils, I will look at you, Narraboth, it may be I will smile at thee. Look at me, Narraboth,

look at me" (15). Her proposal of looking at each other reciprocally is radical within the context of her objectified role, as it implies agency and a break from her usual subjugation under the male gaze.

When Salomé begins to desire Jokanaan, her actions invert the expected dynamics of the gaze. She not only wishes to look upon him, but wants him to look at her with equal measure of desire. She demands his returned gaze and, in doing so, attempts to assert her agency as a desiring subject. Her description of Jokanaan is steeped in romanticised imagery: "Thy body is white like the lilies of a field that the mower hath never mowed. Thy body is white like the snows that lie on the mountains, like the snows that lie on the mountains of Judaea, and come down into the valleys ... There is nothing in the world so white as thy body. Let me touch thy body" (Wilde 21). Salomé maps her erotic yearning onto the land, a gesture that parallels the colonial eroticisation of foreign terrain. Here, Salomé takes on the role of the gazer who desires visual and physical access to the prophet's body. Thus, Salomé will not solely be looked at; she, too, will look. This kind of gazing is one she has never experienced, where she will not simply be the object of desire but a participant.

While her decision to become the gazer might appear to be an assertion of her selfhood, her availability and her perceived willingness to serve as a sexual object are still essential elements to her constitution as the exotic 'Oriental woman'. Both men and women can look. However, it is the female who internalises the gaze. This inversion of the power of the gaze by making Jokanaan its object results in vitriolic condemnation: "Who is this woman who is looking at me? I will not have her look at me". His revulsion towards Salomé is immediate and he reviles her with biblical invectives, calling her the "daughter of Babylon," and the "whore of Sodom" (Wilde 23). These references mark her as a sexually threatening figure, and even her status as a virgin does not shield her from these condemnations. In the Orientalist imagination, she is permitted to be both

untouched and lascivious. Though a virgin, it is completely acceptable for the Oriental Salomé to be painted as lustful and dangerous. As the Western fantasy of the ‘Oriental woman’, she can collapse categories of purity and depravity, and invite both possession and moral outrage.

Salomé’s desire, once expressed, becomes a site of anxiety and fatal transgression as her erotic agency is dangerous and excessive. The young Syrian guard, who is in love with her, pleads with her, crying, “look not at this man, look not at him” (Wilde 23). Her amorous desire for Jokanaan blinds her to her external reality, as she does not acknowledge the young Syrian’s distress. Distraught by her rejection, he commits suicide. Salomé does not even acknowledge his death, emphasising her detachment from the moral world. She repeats her demand to Jokanaan, “Let me kiss thy mouth” three times and declares “I will kiss thy mouth” seven times in this scene, while the guards around her recoil at the macabre of the scene that has unfolded before their eyes. Her repetitions appear almost incantatory, revealing the ritualistic nature her obsession has taken on. In the final scene, Wilde repeats this incantatory pattern as Salomé repeats her demands to a mortified and pleading Herod: “Give me the head of Jokanaan” (Wilde 59, 61). Her obsession evokes the kind of overpowering erotic fixation Orientalist discourse would often ascribe to non-Western women: ungoverned, irrational, and sensual to the point of madness. Salomé’s erotic agency, then, is both the catalyst for the play’s action and the reason for her eventual destruction. Her desire is portrayed as a profound affront to patriarchal and colonial systems of representation, and when she begins to act upon her desires, she is vilified and ultimately erased.

The fatal dance of the seven veils, which happens in the final scene of the play, is a symbolically loaded moment that functions as both a seduction and an execution. It is a fatal performance through which Salomé weaponises her objectification to fulfil her amorous desire for Jokanaan. Salomé’s dance is a deliberate manipulation of the male gaze. Therefore, while it is

sensual to please Herod's amorous gaze, it is also saturated with brutality and agency. Herod watches her intently throughout her performance, his gaze charged with lust and expectation. Salomé instrumentalises that gaze: she consents to become the object of desire in order to bring death to the one man who would not look at her with desire and instead looked at her with disdain. In this moment, she embraces the full catalogue of Orientalist projections. She is at once the exotic dancing girl, the courtesan, the seductress and the femme fatale. Her visual aspect is, as a whole, a reduction of the 'Oriental woman' figure. However, she does not embrace these roles to conform to them, but to subvert their logic and redirect their power toward her ends.

Salomé's reduction to the fetishised 'Oriental woman' is thus mediated through the projections of those who observe her. These projections are particularly evident in the symbolism of the veils. The muslin veil and fans that Salomé hides her face behind at the beginning of the play, and the veils that cover her body as she dances, add to her role as the object of the gaze. They are not only visual motifs but symbolic instruments that stage the Western fantasy of unveiling the East. The veil, within Orientalist discourse, has long functioned as a metonym for the impenetrability and unknowability of the East and has elicited both fascination and frustration from the occidental viewer. As Yeğenoğlu states, the veil "conceals the Orient and Oriental woman from apprehension; it hides the real Orient and keeps its truth from Western knowledge/apprehension. It is also a metaphor of membrane, serving as a screen around which Western fantasies of penetration revolve" (47). The veiled Eastern woman thus becomes a screen for the projection of Western male fantasy, a figure whose visual inaccessibility paradoxically intensifies her erotic appeal. The veil thus becomes a trope through which Western fantasies of penetration into the mysteries of the Orient are achieved. The veil signifies both modesty and mystery, and its role during a dance of seduction plays into the fantasy of conquest.

While the play lacks a literal white male figure, it was written and staged for a white, European audience whose pre-existing assumptions about the oriental and exotic Salomé would have shaped their reception of the text. The erotic charge of the performance thus rests not only within the diegesis of the play, but also within its spectatorship. Furthermore, Jokanaan, the sole figure whom Salomé desires, is framed as a paragon of moral and physical purity and is associated with the Christian West. His body is described in divine, luminous imagery, and his rejection of Salomé is entrenched in religious condemnation. His gaze, unlike Herod's, is not desirous. Instead, he sees her, judges her, and denies her. He denies her not just as a woman, but as a symbolic embodiment of the East, of temptation and the fallen. It is his gaze that is most important, and it is his rejection that drives Salomé to bring about Jokanaan's terrible end in the play.

Though Wilde's *Salomé* suggests that the titular character exerts control over her body and desires, the tragedy of the play ultimately pivots on her inability to elicit the gaze of the one man who resists her: Jokanaan. Jokanaan does not elicit the threat of sexual desire because he is not perceived by the audience as belonging to the Orient. He is the one character unmarked by Orientalist fantasy, cast instead as a figure of Christian morality and Western spiritual authority. His refusal to return Salomé's gaze interrupts the sexual economy of the play, rendering her desire unfulfilled. This lack becomes the driving force of the narrative when, in a climactic act of grotesque retribution, Salomé kisses the severed head of Jokanaan, fulfilling her obsessive promise: "I will kiss thy mouth, Jokanaan. I will kiss thy mouth" (Wilde 23). Of course, this inversion of power and conquest, where the 'Oriental woman' is dominant over the Christian man, cannot be sustained within the logic of the play. It is swiftly corrected by her execution, which is ordered by Herod, the patriarchal and monarchical authority, thereby restoring the moral and political order that her transgression disrupted.

Salomé's portrayal meets with Bryan S. Turner's assertion that "the East appears in the literature of the western imagination as the forbidden Other, which is simultaneously repulsive, seductive and attractive" (1). Within the decadent palace of Herod, forbidden desires can proliferate: the homosexual longing of the Page for the Syrian, the incestuous lust of Herod for his stepdaughter, and Salomé's transgressive desire for Jokanaan. However, it is the 'Oriental woman' who must ultimately bear the weight of these fantasies. She is the crucible for all that is perverse and dangerous in the Western imagination. Her body becomes a symbolic site akin to Kukuanaaland, the colonised space of conquest and exoticism. As she dares to reverse the roles and desires, and becomes the desiring subject rather than the desired object, her punishment is rendered not only inevitable but morally justified within the colonial gaze of the European audience.

Conclusion

The play thus reveals how the construction of the 'Oriental woman' functions to legitimise the sexual exploitation and objectification of women through the spectre of the male gaze and sexual fantasy. Salomé is no Victorian Moll Flanders who can earn the reader's admiration for her cunning, street smarts and guile despite her moral ambiguity. She is reduced to a type: an archetypal figure defined by her race, gender, religion, and colonial subjectivity. These identity categories intersect to produce a fantasy that both invites and punishes female desire, primarily when expressed by a racialised body.

Salomé's refusal to remain a passive object, her act of looking, desiring, and ultimately possessing the body of the Christian prophet Jokanaan, constitutes a radical reversal of the male gaze. This reversal is punished through her violent death, reaffirming the patriarchal order. Ultimately, Salomé is constructed as the ultimate object of the dangerous gaze. She is to be looked at with desire, with revulsion and with fear. When she transgresses, she is treated with the

satisfaction of punishment. Her story does not resolve in redemption but in silencing through the violent termination of a body that dared to look back. Thus, Wilde's *Salomé* serves not only as a tragedy but also as a text that reveals the history of Orientalist representation, where desire, race, and violence intertwine beneath the veil of aestheticism.

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